

Improvement of Plasticity by Tailoring Secondary Phases in Ti-rich Ti-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni BMG Matrix Composites

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1. Introduction

The emergence of bulk metallic glasses (BMGs) with a unique combination of properties has been an important part of the materials science arena over the past decades. However, monolithic BMGs undergo inhomogeneous plastic deformation under loading at room temperature, during which localized regions of shear bands are formed where the plastic flow is confined. This plastic flow allows only a few shear bands to be active and results in catastrophic failure. This instability severely restricts applications of BMGs. To solve this problem, various composite microstructures have been pursued with the notion that if these localized shear bands are diffused or arrested within the microstructure, a higher macroscopic plastic strain can be achieved. However, there is a lack of systematic approach for modulation of secondary phases of in-situ BMG matrix composites. In the present study, we further extend the limit of plasticity in Ti-rich Ti-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni BMG composites by tailoring the combination of mixing enthalpies of the atomic pairs and process optimization. [1]

2. Experimental

Ti-(Y,Nb)-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni BMG composites were produced by rapid quenching, injection casting, and unidirectional solidification methods, which exhibit different cooling conditions during solidification.

The structure of the samples was examined preliminarily by XRD for a 2θ range of 10-90°. Thermal analysis of the samples was carried out by DSC. The microstructures of the samples were examined using the TEM linked with an EDS. The thin foil specimens for TEM were prepared by Ar ion milling using PIPS at 2.6 keV and ~5 mA with liquid nitrogen cooling. Compressive test was performed at a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The strain was determined from the platen displacement after correction for the machine compliance.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Phase separation

The minor addition (MA) of Y (Y-Ti: +58 kJ/mol) induced phase separation (PS) into Y-rich crystalline particles and Ti-rich amorphous matrix, which can be evaluated by DSC and XRD analysis (not shown). On the other hand, a large amount (>10 at.%) of Nb (Y-Ti: +10 kJ/mol) addition causes dramatic deterioration of GFA, which shows a side effect of addition of an element having positive enthalpy of mixing (PEM). This result indicates that the development of a phase separating metallic glass faces is an apparent paradox with the GFA. To confirm the occurrence of PS, the microstructure of the rapidly solidified (a) $\text{Ti}_{41}\text{Y}_{14}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Be}_{18}\text{Cu}_9\text{Ni}_8$ and (b) $\text{Ti}_{14}\text{Y}_{41}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Be}_{18}\text{Cu}_9\text{Ni}_8$ ribbons was observed using TEM. Fig. 1 shows TEM BF images and SADP patterns for (a) $\text{Ti}_{41}\text{Y}_{14}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Be}_{18}\text{Cu}_9\text{Ni}_8$ and (b) $\text{Ti}_{14}\text{Y}_{41}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Be}_{18}\text{Cu}_9\text{Ni}_8$ ribbons, respectively. The present results show that a high cooling rate provides a sufficient undercooling for the wide composition ranges of Ti-Y-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni alloy system melt to fall into the metastable

Fig 1. TEM bright-field image and SADP patterns

liquid immiscibility gap followed by separation into Ti-rich and Y-rich liquids. Due to the relatively high GFA of Ti-rich liquid and relatively low GFA of Y-rich liquid, the Ti-rich liquid mainly solidifies into amorphous phase and Y-rich liquid mainly solidify into crystalline phase in whole composition range.

3.2 Tailoring combination of constituent elements

The thermodynamics of glass formation point to increased instability of the system with increasing difference of the heat of mixing among constituent elements. Thus, it has been recently shown that tailoring the combination of constituent elements influences the local structural heterogeneity. [2] Based on this concept, small amount (up to 6 at.%) of alloying elements having different value of PEM with Ti, i.e. Y (Y-Ti: +58 kJ/mol) or Nb (Nb-Ti: +10 kJ/mol) is added in $\text{Ti}_{55}\text{Zr}_{18}\text{Be}_{14}\text{Cu}_7\text{Ni}_6$ alloy ($D_{\max}=2$ mm). The HRTEM results for $\text{Ti}_{55-(x,y)}(\text{Y}_x, \text{Nb}_y)\text{Zr}_{18}\text{Be}_{14}\text{Cu}_7\text{Ni}_6$ ($0 \leq x, y \leq 6$ at.%) rod samples with 1 mm diameter indicates that MA of elements having positive enthalpy of mixing can induce different degree of instability in the single amorphous matrix depending on the amount of repulsive interaction energy. In particular, MA of element having relatively small PEM can cause to the formation of composite with nanoscale I phase particle in Ti-rich Ti-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni alloys.

3.3 Mechanical properties

The effect of Nb and Y on the mechanical properties of the Ti-rich Ti-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni alloy has been evaluated by compression test. Fig. 2 shows the compressive stress-strain curves for $\text{Ti}_{55-(x,y)}(\text{Y}_x, \text{Nb}_y)\text{Zr}_{18}\text{Be}_{14}\text{Cu}_7\text{Ni}_6$ rod samples with 1 mm diameter. When compared with the compressive fracture strain (ϵ_f) of $\text{Ti}_{55}\text{Zr}_{18}\text{Be}_{14}\text{Cu}_7\text{Ni}_6$ BMG ($\sim 2.95 \pm 0.2$ %), MA of Y (2 at.%) decreased the plastic strain slightly, further increase of Y (≥ 4 at.%) resulted in nearly zero plasticity as a result of PS. On the other hand, MA of Nb (up to 4 at.%) significantly increased the ϵ_f ($\sim 9.35 \pm 0.2$ %), and then decreased down to $\sim 6.8 \pm 0.2$ % for $y=6$. It can be realized that the ϵ_f for $x=4$ is much larger than that of Nb-free $\text{Ti}_{50}\text{Zr}_{15}\text{Be}_{18}\text{Cu}_9\text{Ni}_8$ BMG having 1-2 nm scale quenched in icosahedral nuclei (~ 4.9 %). It can be noticed that since nanoscale particles are free of defects, the isolated and homogeneously distributed nanocrystals in the amorphous matrix can harden the and affect local viscous flow during deformation.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves obtained from the uniaxial compression test of $\text{Ti}_{55-(x,y)}(\text{Y}_x, \text{Nb}_y)\text{Zr}_{18}\text{Be}_{14}\text{Cu}_7\text{Ni}_6$

4. Conclusion

The present study shows MA of elements having PEM with constituent elements cause different degree of heterogeneity in the system depending on the amount of repulsive interaction energy among the constituent elements. First, a large amount of Y addition can lead to the liquid state PS in Ti-rich Ti-Zr-Be-Cu-Ni alloy, while a large amount of Nb addition lead to deteriorate GFA. Secondly, the MA of Y similarly induced PS into Y-rich crystalline particles and Ti-rich amorphous matrix, while the MA of Nb led to the nanocrystallization of I-phase in Ti-rich BMGs with quenched in icosahedral nuclei. In particular, it can be noticed that the nanoscale I-phase particle developed by tailoring combination of constituent elements can enhance the plasticity in Ti-based BMGs, which explain the beneficial effects of MA of elements having PEM. This concept is considered to be effective even in composite design in other BMG systems with quenched in icosahedral nuclei.

5. References

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